

What's Beyond Twitter / X?

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Working within the higher education sector, particularly within the third space, can be an isolating experience with limited opportunities for professional development (Silvey et al., 2018; Trust et al., 2017). As such, the development of a Professional Learning Network (PLN) takes on heightened importance for third space professionals. Trust et al. (2016) define a PLN as a “uniquely personalized, complex system of interactions consisting of people, resources, and digital tools that support ongoing learning and professional growth” (p. 28). We commence this article with the opportunity for you to meet us, the presenters, to hear about how we leverage our professional networks. More information about us is also available via [our website](#).

Figure 1: How we leverage our professional networks

The use of social media is one of the digital tools that can be used by third space professionals to expand their PLN beyond the walls of their institution. During the pandemic, Twitter was the “go to” platform for learning designers to ask questions, offer support, share resources and communicate with those in other institutions globally. Our interest at that time resulted in us undertaking research, scraping and analysing data from the TELedvisors Twitter feed, to better understand the social media platform and pandemic conversations during this pivotal time. We concluded that Twitter was an underutilised, non-hierarchical, open platform for learning designers to share their ideas, promote their work and to have conversations with a global community of like-minded individuals (Ng et al., 2023).

What was once a thriving, central, global gathering space has since been shattered, resulting in a fragmented social media landscape (Carrigan, 2023). Our paper “Look who’s talking: Professional conversations of learning designers on Twitter during COVID-19” (Ng et al., 2023), situates use

of the platform as an important component of a learning designer's professional learning network, and helped to set the scene for our topic discussions over the fortnight of the Slowposium.

We were interested in discussing with the community what's beyond Twitter/X? What do people use now beyond Twitter? How do we build and sustain communities of practice? How do we promote and share our work? How do we find out about professional development opportunities? How do we think about and form professional learning networks and how do we connect at a more international and global level?

During the Slowposium, participants responded to a series of provocations and polls, and engaged in very lively and active discussion, reflecting on what platforms they were using to connect with the community and why they were involved or not involved. The discussion forum noted the exodus from Twitter, mourning the loss of the critical mass the community had and the fragmentation of social media with the community using separate platforms. The result from the polls put LinkedIn out in front as platform most used to connect with others professionally, as well as platform most used for professional development, followed by Twitter/X and Bluesky. Contributions to the Padlet wall resource and in the discussion forum included a Bluesky starter pack and basic explainer resource, and tips for using LinkedIn for peer learning and building connections.

The high level of engagement in our session received formal acknowledgement at the in-person Third Space Symposium event. Reflecting a year on, while Bluesky seems like the closest thing to Twitter, it hasn't really taken off. Perhaps we've become more used to using LinkedIn to network and build community than we had a year ago? The drive for connection, support, dialogue and community, that was a common theme expressed across posts during the Slowposium, strongly remains.

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